

PSYCHODIAGNOSTICS AND PSYCHOCORRECTION OF PROFESSIONAL DEFORMITY IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

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Abstract. Considering professional deformations as changes in the existing structure of activity and personality, negatively affecting labor productivity and interaction with other participants in this process, one cannot disagree that there is an urgent need to introduce an academic discipline on this issue into the state educational standard not only for student teachers

Keywords: psychodiagnostics, psychocorrection, professional deformity, method.

INTRODUCTION

The methodological basis of the academic discipline should be the following questions: the category of “professional deformations” in psychology; factors influencing the occurrence of professional deformations; typical consequences of professional deformations; specifics of mental hygiene, psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrection of professional deformations. Particular attention should be paid to the selection of psychodiagnostic procedures, active forms of work (exercises, games), necessary not only for the purpose of deeper assimilation of theoretical material and satisfying the need for self-knowledge of future specialists, but also for the purpose of a more complete and comprehensive understanding of the problem itself professional deformations, and not just this

category. Test assignments should help reveal the axiological and acmeological potential of future specialists in accordance with innovative training.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We offer future psychologists the following tasks: write a review of one of the books on the list read; create a crossword puzzle based on a set of course concepts; collect in an envelope the completed forms of all techniques carried out during practical classes and be ready to answer questions; write your own psychological portrait based on the results of psychological diagnostics; based on your own psychological portrait, write self-recommendations aimed at continuing psychodiagnostics, implementing psychoprophylaxis, psychocorrection and psychoprognosis; draw up a summary of a psychoprophylactic lesson; test all course methods on three teachers and three psychologists, compile their psychological portraits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of diagnostics of the characteristics of professional deformations, in general, and emotional and/or physical exhaustion, depersonalization and reduction of personal achievements, in particular, of 3816 future and working psychologists and teachers.

1) the average level of severity of professional deformations in general is 60.07 among psychology students and student teachers; 60.67 – among working psychologists and teachers; 60.37 - for all subjects);

2) emotional exhaustion is practically not observed in all subjects (level below average) (19.39; 21.24 and 20.32, respectively);

3) depersonalization, as well as emotional exhaustion, has a level of severity below average (9.76, 9.58 and 9.67, respectively);

4) such a component as the reduction of personal achievements is alarming and makes one seriously think: it is for this that all subjects have a level of expression above average (30.92; 29.85 and 30.39, respectively. All subjects are

currently time do not yet see that thanks to their work (study) they have already done a lot of really valuable things in life; not everyone has plans for the future and believes in their implementation; it is not always easy to create an atmosphere of goodwill and cooperation in the team; some subjects do not are confident that their work is needed by people; not everyone knows how to find the right solution in conflict situations that arise when dealing with colleagues, subordinates and classmates; they understand well how subordinates, colleagues and classmates feel, and try to take this into account in the interests of the cause.

Thus, the demand for knowledge on psychohygiene of professional personality deformation is associated with the dynamism of the socio-economic situation in Russia and abroad: intensive economic development; cardinal changes in the labor market and the situation in it; the need for professional mobilization and competitiveness of workers; the emergence of new professions and specialties aimed at highly qualified specialists; technical progress, etc.

Psychohygiene of professional personality deformation acts as part of general hygiene, developing measures to preserve and strengthen a person's neuropsychic health, his acmeological potential in the process of professional activity, and psychoprophylaxis of professional personality deformation, the main goals of which are the elimination of external and internal - external factors that adversely affect the human psyche, his acmeological potential and the results of professional activity, and the use of external and internal factors that positively influence the subject of professional activity and its effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

It is important not only to study the influence of various environmental conditions (industrial, domestic, social) on the human psyche, but also to develop optimal standards for work, rest and living (introduce into practice measures to strengthen the nervous system, increase its resistance to harmful influences and ensure the best conditions for the normal development and functioning of the

human psyche), as well as to promote psychohygienic knowledge. Particular attention must be paid to early diagnosis of professional personality deformations, identification of factors that impede successful professional adaptation and professional growth of workers, development of preventive and corrective measures and their implementation not only in professional activities, but also in the process of professional training of specialists. A practical psychologist is called upon to help others and himself.

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